

Alternative Quantum Entropy Including Stochastic Potential Hits

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In the literature, $-k [W^*(x)W(x)] \ln[W^*(x)W(x)]$ is often used to compute spatial quantum entropy, given a wavefunction $W(x)$. An analogous expression holds for momentum entropy. In a previous note (1), we argued one may use Shannon's entropy with $P(p/x)P(x)$ instead of $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ which leads to an entropy for bound states of:

$$-k \{ -W(x)W(x) \ln(W) + i W(x) x \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + \text{Sum over } p \ a(-p)a(p) \ln[a(p)] \}$$

where b is constant related to the normalization of $\exp(ikx)$. In this note, we argue that this alternative entropy may be too simplistic because $P(x)$ implies a quantum particle exists in a region Δx near x . In this region, a stochastic potential hit should occur, so in this note we suggest that $P(p1/x)P(p2/x)P(x)$ ((1)) may represent a more complete probability in place of $P(p/x)P(x)$.

((1)) becomes: $a(p1)a(p2) \exp(ip1x)\exp(ip2x)$.

In analogy, spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ is based on a relative probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to have a particle with momentum p at x . This particle then receives a momentum hit from the potential and changes into $a(p1)\exp(ip1x)$. Thus, one has joint relative probability: $a(p)a(p1)\exp(ipx)\exp(ip1x)$ ((1)) and one sums over these to obtain the spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ which itself is a probability. We argue that ((1)) constitutes a probability although it is normalized only if one sums on $p, p1$ and integrates on x . We obtain the corresponding entropy and find that if one maximizes it using the constraint for a harmonic oscillator, one obtains the momentum ground state. Thus, there may be a link between this entropy and the Schrodinger equation.

Alternative Entropy

Traditionally, $-k [W^*W] \ln(W^*W)$ is used as spatial Shannon's density where $W^*(x)W(x)=P(x)$ i.e. spatial density. In a previous note, we suggested one may use $P(p/x)P(x)$ instead of $P(x)$ when calculating Shannon's entropy. One benefit, we argue, is that this new entropy allows for nonzero entropy to exist for plane waves and plane waves with a phase shift (e.g. the Bohm Aharonov effect). The new entropy is:

$$\text{Integral } dx \frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + \text{Integral } dx \text{ Sum } p1,p2 \ \ln[a(p1)a(p2)] a(p1)a(p2) \exp(i (p1+p2)x) \quad ((2))$$

Or

$$\text{Integral } dx \frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + \text{Sum over } p \ b \ \ln[a(-p)a(p)] a(p)a(-p) \quad ((2))$$

The second term is the usual momentum space entropy where b is related to normalization of the basis function $\exp(ikx)$.

One may note that ((2)) allows for nonzero entropy from plane waves and plane waves with phase shifts while $[W^*W] \ln(W^*W)$ does not. It is also interesting to note that $[dW/dx]/W(x)$ is the average momentum at x , thus the entropy contains a kinematical term.

In a previous note, we pointed out that for the ground state of the harmonic oscillator, $-[W^*W] \ln(W^*W) = 2ax^*x W^*W$ because W oscillator ground state = $\exp(-a x^*x)$. Thus, traditional spatial entropy is proportional $V(x) W^*(x)W(x)$. This relationship, however, is still present in dW/dx which is also proportional to $V(x)W^*(x)W(x)$. Furthermore, the second term in ((2)) is the kinetic energy integral if one uses $a(p) = \exp(-b_1 p^*p)$ i.e. the ground state oscillator result.

Ground State Quantum Oscillator and Traditional Spatial and Momentum Entropies

The ground state quantum oscillator is interesting because its spatial and momentum wavefunctions squared i.e. spatial and momentum densities are of the same form of those for the classical statistical mechanical case i.e. $W(x) = C \exp(-ax^*x)$ and $a(p) = C_1 \exp(-b_1 p^*p)$. In the classical case, entropy is maximized with respect to constraints. The classical case, however, is based on two body scattering as the underlying stochastic process whereas in quantum mechanics a particle scatters or receives hits from a stochastic potential, we argue.

As a first step, consider the relationship between the ground state oscillator problem and traditional spatial and momentum entropies: $-[W^*W] \ln(W^*W)$ and $-[a(p)a(p)] \ln[a(p)a(p)]$.

First, we use the constraint that $\int dx V(x) W^*(x)W(x) = .5 \text{ Energy}$ and let $W^*(x) = W(x)$ together with the two Lagrange multipliers $b_1 W^*W$ and $b_2 V(x) W(x)W(x)$. Maximizing:

$$[W^*W] \ln(W^*W) + b_1 WW + b_2 V(x) W(x)W(x) \quad ((2))$$

with respect to density WW yields: $W = C \exp(-V(x)b_2)$ ((3)) which is the classical statistical mechanical result. This only applies to the oscillator due to the constraint $V(x)W(x)W(x)$ used.

One may argue that for a spatial entropy, there should also be a momentum entropy given by: $-k a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ with the constraint $b_1 a(p)a(p)$ and $b_2 p^*p/2m a(p)a(p)$

where: Total kinetic energy in the system (1 dimension) = $2 \int dp p^*p/2m a(p)a(p)$ for a bound state system. Maximizing with respect to $a(p)a(p)$ yields:

$$a(p) = C_1 \exp(- p^*p/2m b_2) \quad ((3))$$

This is the ground state oscillator result, which is also the classical statistical mechanical result. An issue remaining is the constraint: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. This must hold for the two results above, which it does (for the ground state oscillator), but no constraint was added to ensure this.

Consider another example, namely the maximization of:

$$W^2 \ln(W) + 2 \int a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)) + b_1 \left[\int W W + \int p^2/2m a(p)a(p) \right] + b_2 \int a(p)a(p) + b_3 \int W(x)W(x) \quad ((4))$$

with respect to W and $a(p)$ as independent entities (even though they are not). Here, b_2 and b_3 (constraints) ensure that $\int dp a(p)a(p)$ and $\int dx W(x)W(x)$ are both normalized to 1. Let $W \rightarrow W + \delta W$ and $a(p) \rightarrow a(p) + \delta a(p)$. Given that W and $a(p)$ are linked, δW and $\delta a(p)$ are linked.

If one replaces W and $a(p)$ in ((4)) with $W + \delta W$ and $a(p) + \delta a(p)$ and wishes the delta term to vanish, then using: $\ln(W + \delta W) = \ln W + \delta W/W$ and a similar expression for $a(p)$, the delta terms from the logarithms with the b_2 and b_3 constraints give:

$$2 \int a(p) + 2 \int W(x) + b_2 \int a(p) + b_3 \int W(x) \quad ((5a))$$

and those from terms which are not logarithms with constraint b_1 :

$$4 \int W \ln(W) + 4 \int a(p) \ln(a(p)) + b_1 \left[2 \int W W + \int p^2/2m 2 \int a(p) \right] \quad ((5b))$$

A solution to ((5a)), ((5b)) is: $\ln(W) = c_1 \int W$ and $\ln(a(p)) = c_2 \int p^2/2m$

This corresponds to the solution for the ground state harmonic oscillator. One may argue that $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ were treated as independent, but one may implicitly assume that $\delta a(p)$ and $\delta W(x)$ are linked because $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

In the above example, one may question why spatial and momentum entropies were added? A priori, it seems there is no reason to combine the two and maximize. We next consider the alternative entropy obtained using $P(p_1/x)P(p_2/x)P(x)$ to see its relationship with the ground state oscillator solution.

Alternative Entropy and the Ground State Oscillator

The alternative entropy suggested in this note is:

$$\int dx dW/dx dW/dx + \sum_p b \ln[a(-p)a(p)] a(p)a(-p) \quad ((2))$$

Assume $a(p)=a(-p)$ and consider specifically the oscillator problem for which the energy constraint may be written as $b_1 \int a(p)a(p)p^2/2m$ because total kinetic energy equals total potential energy. Then, integrate the first term of ((2)) over x and maximize with respect to $a(p)$:

$$\int a(p)a(p) p^2/2m + b \ln[a(p)a(p)] \int a(p)a(p) + b_1 \int a(p)a(p)p^2/2m \quad ((6))$$

Here b is related to the normalization of the basis function $\exp(ipx)$. Maximization yields the ground state of the quantum oscillator.

Next, consider the more general situation with the constraints $b_1 \int W W V(x) + p^2/2m a(p)a(p) + b_2 \int W W + b_3 \int a(p)a(p)$ and maximize with respect to W and $a(p)$ as independent objects (which they are not):

$$\int dx dW/dx dW/dx + \sum_{p} b \ln[a(-p)a(p)] \int a(p)a(p) + b_1 \int W W V(x) + p^2/2m a(p)a(p) + b_2 \int W W + b_3 \int a(p)a(p)$$

This yields: $-d/dx d/dx W + b_2 W + b_1 V = 0$ and $a(p) = C \exp(-p^2/2m C^2)$

The first equation is of the form of the time independent Schrodinger equation and the latter is the momentum wavefunction for the ground state oscillator. Thus, one again obtains the ground state oscillator solution, but the Schrodinger equation form also appears in this result.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest there may be an alternative expression for Shannon's quantum entropy obtained using probability $= P(p_1/x)P(p_2/x)P(x)$. This leads to:

$$\text{Entropy} = \int dx dW/dx dW/dx + \sum_{p} b \ln[a(-p)a(p)] \int a(p)a(-p) \quad ((2))$$

In earlier notes, we only used $P(p_1/x)P(x)$ when trying to formulate a new entropy. The entropy expression ((2)) may be maximized with respect to constraints and the ground state oscillator solution obtained. It is also linked to the Schrodinger equation as shown above. In addition, it yields results for plane waves.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Spatial Quantum Entropy (preprint, zenodo, 2020)